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DONAU SOJA
Promoting a sustainable and European protein supply

Within a five-year Strategic partnership Donau Soja and ADA support the development of sustainable and inclusive value chains for non-GMO soy in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, Moldavia and Ukraine

Second European Soy Monitor available now

The second European Soy Monitor was published by the Sustainable Trade Initiative (IDH). It gives an update on the transition towards responsible and deforestation-free soy in the EU-28, Norway, and Switzerland.

In 2018, 38% of soybean meal consumption in Europe was FEFAC SSG compliant and 19% was deforestation-free. This can be considered the start of a shift that requires an ongoing drive by all actors to reimagine supply chains.

DONAU SOJA is part of the solution: We are happy to contribute to the growing volumes of deforestation-free and conversion-free soya. Also, the trends confirm that we are moving in the right direction: deforestation-free commitments will impact the supply chain more intensively in the coming years, reducing the carbon footprint is increasingly important, sourcing of European cultivated soya will further increase.

[Find out more](#) about the status quo and future trends in sustainable European soya sourcing.

Europe Soya protein concentrate from Finland for Europe

This June, multi-stage soya processor **Nordic Soya Oy** located in Uusikaupunki in Southern Finland achieved their first Europe Soya certificate. Another significant partner joined the movement of a deforestation-free and non-GM protein supply from and for Europe. The plant will supply the European fish feed, pet food as well as the agricultural sector with high-quality non-GM SPC, meal, and oil under the Europe Soya certification. Janne Lukkarinen, Commercial Director at Nordic Soya Oy, states that the “transition to European origin soya was a natural step for Nordic Soya as our aquaculture customers in Northern Europe start to require sustainable, European origin feed raw materials. By joining DONAU SOJA we wanted to become part of the solution to help Europe become more self-sufficient in plant protein, in a sustainable way.” DONAU SOJA Organisation is excited to have Nordic Soya on board!

Open letter to protect the Amazon

The Amazon is one of the most vital landscapes on our planet: it not only contains 30% of world’s rainforest but it is also home to 10% of all known species. More crucially, the Amazon plays a critical role in regulating global climate, the water cycle as well as its role in system resilience which is fundamental for planetary health.

The “Open letter on the protection of the Amazon” released on 19th May recognises the importance of the Amazon biome and the need to mobilise against the Bolsonaro administration’s 2633/2020 land reform bill, which aims to legalise the private occupation of public lands, and encourages further land grabbing and widespread deforestation.

41 companies and organisations, including livestock and feed producers, investors, retailers (ALDI, Burger King, Co-op Switzerland, Marks & Spencer, Migros, REWE,...) and of course DONAU SOJA, signed the open letter to the member of the Brazilian National Congress who demanded to drop this plan. Economic development and environmental protection are a unity!

Your company can still sign the open letter and add further weight to the message that businesses care about preventing measures that will encourage further deforestation in the Amazon biome.

Find the open letter [here](#) if you are interested to sign.

How to control weeds between the rows?

Soybeans are commonly grown in Europe in rows with a width of about 50 cm. Wide row allow a proper mechanical weed control using for example cultivators. This management practice is essential to achieve a clean soya bean field and a good yield. Depending on the soil conditions a field needs to be treated a couple of times. **Key points for soya bean producers are summarised** by the Institute of Fields and Vegetable Crops Novi Sad in a Legumes Translated practice note [here](#).

Practical field test in Moldova: sowing organic soybeans into a field of green rye

Heavy rains have damaged many fields during the last weeks. Fields with summer crops in wide rows were more vulnerable to the destructive force of the rain due to the relatively large unprotected surface between the rows. One good way to deal with that is to seed soybean a layer of mulch and so did it our colleague in Moldova on 11th May. On the farm of Mr. Mi they have sown organic soybeans into a field of green rye. If you have questions about this field test, please reach out to [Ms Ela Malai](#).

The field test is supported by DONAU SOJA and ProDidactica in the framework of EU funded and ADA implemented Program for Developing of Rural Areas in Moldova. Follow [this link](#) to see a video about establishing the field test.

Practice videos available for crop management in soy farming

Crop management videos for soya farming are now available on the YouTube Channel 'Legume Hub'. They cover the most essential practices: inoculation, seeding, mechanical weed control, harvesting, processing, etc. **Subtitles are currently available for all video German and English and in some cases also in French, Ukrainian and Russian.** This service is supported by the EU-funded project 'Legumes Translated'. Subscribe to the channel to stay informed about new videos.

The screenshot shows the YouTube channel page for 'Legume Hub', which has 13 subscribers. The channel is subscribed to. The 'VIDEOS' tab is selected, showing three video uploads:

- Sojaanbau für Tofu** (5:07): 14 Aufrufe • vor 1 Woche. Untertitel.
- Impfung von Sojasaatgut** (7:36): 6 Aufrufe • vor 1 Woche. Untertitel.
- Soja richtig dreschen** (7:46): 13 Aufrufe • vor 2 Wochen. Untertitel.

SAVE THE DATE Extraordinary General Assembly & Networking Event 2020

It is our great pleasure to announce that the DONAU SOJA Extraordinary General Assembly & Networking Event 2020 will take place on **19th November 2020** in Vienna.

General Assembly (Members only):

Venue: Agricultural Product Exchange (Börse für landwirtschaftliche Produkte), Taborstraf: 10, 1020 Vienna

Time: 09.30 - 12:30

In the afternoon, the DONAU SOJA Association will host a networking event open to all stakeholders. This is an excellent opportunity to meet again and discuss current topics.

Networking afternoon:

Venue: Agricultural Product Exchange (Börse für landwirtschaftliche Produkte), Taborstraße 10, 1020 Vienna

Time: 14.30-16:30

We are looking forward to having you there!

Your Donau Soja Team

PS: The extraordinary General Assembly follows the “General Assembly without physical participation”, which took place under corona circumstances on 28 April 2020. The Extraordinary General Assembly of 19 November will elect new bodies for a period of 2 years, replacing the provisional bodies re-elected temporarily during the corona lockdown.

SAVE THE DATE**CSI Webinar Land use change and soya**

On **7th September 2020**, the Collaborative Soy Initiative invites you to a webinar on Land change and soya, to meet the increasing interest in the carbon footprint of feed products. The webinar aims to answer the following questions: What is a Product Life Cycle Assessment and how is it connected to the Carbon Footprint of soya? How to integrate and calculate Life Cycle Assessment emissions based on available data?

In the webinar, the relevant legal frameworks will be explored and guidelines, including the EU Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) as well as the renewal of the FEFAC Soy Sourcing Guidelines. Dive into the methodology and learn more about guidelines for land-change and limitation factors.

Register [here](#) and find out more about the webinar and the [Collaborative Soy Initiative](#).

A graphic for a webinar titled "SAVE THE DATE WEBINAR Land use change and soy". The text is centered on a light background with colorful geometric shapes (triangles) in the corners. A red banner at the top contains the text "SAVE THE DATE". Below it, "WEBINAR" is written in bold blue letters, followed by "Land use change and soy" in a smaller blue font. Underneath, it says "Organized by the Collaborative Soy Initiative". A grey rounded rectangle contains the date and time: "Date: 07.09, Monday | Time: 2pm CET". At the bottom right, the "COLLABORATIVE SOY INITIATIVE" logo is displayed with a small triangle icon.

SAVE THE DATE

WEBINAR

Land use change and soy

Organized by the Collaborative Soy Initiative

Date: 07.09, Monday | Time: 2pm CET

COLLABORATIVE
SOY INITIATIVE

RECAP: ONLINE EVENTS IN JUNE Field Trip to Ukraine and Buyers Mission 2020

DONAU SOJA organised two successful online events in June. The **virtual Field trip to Ukraine** (organised in partnership with FeedSim Avenir, France) took place on 9th June 2020. The focus of this event was to learn more about "Protein Partnerships" – the European alternative to credits from overseas, to support the production of regional sustainable non-GM soya in Europe, with a strong focus on the potential of partnerships in Ukraine. 103 participants took part, most interested in the development of sustainable value chains in Europe! Various sectors were represented, mainly from retail food, feed companies, and NGOs.

To connect leading market players from DONAU SOJA/EUROPE SOYA certified value chains, DONAU SOJA organised International **online Buyers Mission** on 17th June, 2020 successful event with great participants, they had the opportunity to build up new connections and get the latest updates from the European soya market, a forecast for 20/21 market season, crop monitoring updates in current trends in developing regional DONAU SOJA/EUROPE SOYA value chains as well as networking platform connecting DONAU SOJA/EUROPE SOYA soybean producers/suppliers with potential buyers. We had more than 50 participants from 12 countries, and 26 B2B meetings.

We want to thank our members and partners for their support and participation! Find more information about the [Buyers mission](#) and the [Field trip to Ukraine](#) on our website.

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